

THE SMARANDACHE CLASS OF PARADOXES

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Let <A> be an attribute, and <Non-A> its negation. Then:

Paradox 1. ALL IS <A>, THE <Non-A> TOO.

Examples:

E11: All is possible, the impossible too.

E12: All are present, the absents too.

E13: All is finite, the infinite too.

Paradox 2. ALL IS <Non-A>, THE <A> TOO.

Examples:

E21: All is impossible, the possible too.

E22: All are absent, the presents too.

E23: All is infinite, the finite too.

Paradox 3. NOTHING IS <A>, NOT EVEN <A>.

Examples:

E31: Nothing is perfect, not even the perfect.

E32: Nothing is absolute, not even the absolute.

E33: Nothing is finite, not even the finite.

Remark: The three kinds of paradoxes are equivalent. They are called: *The Smarandache Class of Paradoxes*.

More generally:

Paradox: ALL (Verb) <A>, THE <Non-A> TOO

(<The Generalized Smarandache Class of Paradoxes>)

Replacing <A> by an attribute, we find a paradox.

Let's analyse the first one (E11):

<All is possible, the impossible too.>

If this sentence is true, then we get that <the impossible is possible too>, which is a contradiction; therefore the sentence is false. (Object Language).

But the sentence may be true because <All is possible> involves that

but the sentence may be true, because "it is possible" involves that "the impossible is possible" <the impossible is possible>, i.e. < it's possible to have impossible things>, which is correct. (M

Of course, from these ones, there are unsuccessful paradoxes, but the proposed method obtain

All is relative, the (theory of) relativity too!

So:

1. The shortest way between two points is the meandering way!
2. The unexplainable is, however, explained by the word: "unexplainable"!

Other Smarandache Paradoxes, Vol. II

Smarandache Sorites Paradoxes

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